

THE IMPORTANCE OF NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN LECTURING

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Abstract. *New pedagogical technologies in the learning process mean the use of optimal methods to achieve the intended goal of a specific educational activity. Undoubtedly, these methods should be proportional to the type of subject, the topic, and the form of the training session. In this regard, there are specific features of lectures, practical classes, and students' independent work on the subject.*

Keywords: *New pedagogical technologies, training session.*

One of the main differences between modern teaching technology and traditional technology is that it is based on a systematic approach to the learning process and personality orientation. This should also be taken into account during lectures. In particular, unlike speeches at various conferences and events, lectures should not be in the form of monologues, but in the conditions of cooperation, interactive environment, and constant dialogue between the lecturer and students. Of course, to ensure this situation, students should be aware of the lecture topic in advance and have appropriate preparation on the issues to be considered. At the Department of Forensic Medicine and Medical Law of the Tashkent Medical Academy, the subject "Medical Law" is taught to 7th-year students of the medical and medical-pedagogical faculties. According to the current curriculum, lectures are scheduled for 6 hours. The main goal of teaching this subject is the acquisition by students of theoretical knowledge and practical skills in the legal aspects of medical activity. It is known that creating interest in the subject in students is an important guarantee of mastering the curriculum. In this regard, the lecturer holds a special place. It is important that they not only know the subject of the subject, but also demonstrate their attitude towards the subject, including respect and interest, to the students during the presentation of the lecture material. Based on this, lectures are delivered live, maintaining constant contact with the audience. The issues discussed in the lectures on "medical law" at the department are connected not with abstract cases, but with examples of specific situations observed in modern medical practice. Students are asked to express their opinions on this particular situation. Usually, the opinions of several students are listened to attentively and attentively, sometimes a small-format discussion is allowed. Then the lecturer summarizes the given ideas and discussion. Consequently, this situation serves the formation in students not only of a creative approach to studying the subject, but also

of a culture of listening to others, primarily opponents, and conducting discussions.

The presentations present current problems in the practical activities of medical workers from the point of view of medical law, paying special attention to their significance, legal assessment, as well as issues of solving problems and eliminating shortcomings. Such problems in medical law include the registration of brain death, the legal basis of traditional medicine, the rights of medical workers, cadaveric donation, and euthanasia. After all, students may encounter these problems in their medical activities in the near future. During the lecture, students can be asked several specific questions regarding some of the identified problems, and their feedback can be obtained (for example, using the "brainstorming" method). The lecturer, noting that the opinions expressed on the problem are different, sometimes contradictory, and contradictory, emphasizes the need to eliminate the problem. All lectures are accompanied by a corresponding presentation. A balanced, high-quality, and comprehensive presentation plays a crucial role in ensuring the effectiveness of the lecture. In particular, to make the presentation engaging and visual, it is necessary to provide as few text-based slides as possible and minimize the text on the slides. It is advisable to present some slides in the form of a cluster, a categorical table, a Venn diagram, a T-table, and a "SWOT" analytical table.

Thus, the alternative use of new pedagogical technologies in lectures contributes to the better assimilation of the topic by students.

LITERARY

1. Voinova M.G. Pedagogical Technologies and Pedagogical Mastery. - T.: "IQTISOD-MOLIYA," 2006.
2. Zhukova E.D. Technology of organizing and implementing students' independent work: workbook. - Ufa: BGPU Publishing House, 2004.
3. Akhmedjonova A. et al. A perfect person is a requirement of the times. T. —Yangi asr avlodil, 2004, -150 pages.
4. Examples of hadiths on morality and ethics. - T.: Fan, 1990. - 170 p.
5. Bobobekov X, Davletshin M.G., Ishmukhamedov R.Zh. et al. System of procedures and main events held in academic lyceums and vocational colleges (Book 2) - T.:Fan, 2005. - 90 p.
- Zunnunov A., Xayrullayev M. Pedagogika tarixi.- T.: Sharq, 2000. - 240 p.
7. Imomnazarov M., Eshmuhamedona M. Fundamentals of Our National Spirituality: (Lecture Texts for Higher Educational Institutions) - T.: Tashkent Islamic University, 2001.-432 6.
8. Ishmuhamedov R.J. Ways to increase the effectiveness of education with the help of innovative technologies (Book 2). - T.: TDPU, 2009. - 108 p.
9. Ishmukhamedov R.Zh. Methodology of using interactive methods and pedagogical

- technologies in the educational process. - T.: RBIMM, 2008. - 68 p. 127.
10. Mukhamedov G.I., Turakulov Kh.A. Scientific and theoretical foundations of modern pedagogical research. Tashkent, —Fan, 2004 - 230 p.
 11. Mahmudov, R. *March to My Destiny*. Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 1992. - 88 p.
 12. Musurmanova O. Spiritual values and youth education. - T.: Teacher, 1996. - 192 p.
 13. Textbook for higher educational institutions. - Tashkent: Fan va texnologiya, 2011.- 482 p.
 14. Dictionary of Pedagogical Terms. Tashkent. "Fan," 2008 - 231 p.
 15. Tolipov O., Usmonboeva M. Applied Foundations of Pedagogical Technologies. - T.: 2006. - 156 p.
 16. Turakulov O.Kh. Methodological Foundations of Creating an Informatized Educational Environment. Tashkent, 2010 - 242 p.
 17. Hikmatnoma. Collection //Collector N.Eshonqulov - T: Cholpon, 1992. - 112 p.
 18. G'aybullayev N.R., Yodgorov R., Mamatqulov R. Pedagogy. Tashkent, 2005.-176 p.
 19. Goziev E. Psychology (Psychology of Youth) /Handbook. - T.: Teacher, 1994. - 223 p.
 20. Khasanboev Zh., Turakulov Kh.A., Alkarov I., Usmanov N.U. Pedagogy. Textbook for higher educational institutions. - Tashkent: Fan va texnologiya, 2011.- 482 p.